

Project CHANGES - Spoke 5

D6.1 – New protocol on analysis, diagnostic, monitoring and planning integrated strategies for historical sites – v2.0

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1	University of Milan - Department of Earth Sciences "ARDITO DESIO"		Andrea Zerboni, Spoke 6 "History, Conservation and Restoration of Cultural Heritage"

Executive Summary

The thematic focus 1 is dedicated to the interdisciplinary interpretation of data deriving from innovative diagnostics and the definition of multimodal protocols for the study of cultural architectural heritage. It aims to develop studies concerning the innovative combination of different diagnostics, regulated by specific protocols, calibrated on the specific problems of characterization and degradation of the factory. The main objectives focus on the application of expeditious laboratory diagnostics on mortars and plasters, application of expeditious on-site diagnostics, both structural and about surface characterization, diagnostic experimentation aimed at the study of deformations/alterations of historical surfaces, diagnostic experimentation related to the chromatic characterization of historical surfaces and their degradation.

The thematic focus 2 revolves around the development of interdisciplinary protocols for architectural and archaeological diagnostics, aiming to experiment and produce innovative methods for documenting technological traces in the field. The main objective is to structure a non-invasive integrated methodology, with a diagnostic approach applicable to the widest possible range of cases. Emphasizing various interpretative levels, ranging from macroscopic to mesoscopic and microscopic analysis, ongoing work involves analysing construction techniques of structures, decorative elements, artistic signs, graphic symbols, and production techniques of objects based on the imprints left by these techniques on processed materials. These technological traces, associated with shared tools and gestures, are observable at different magnifications using optical and digital instrumentation.

The activity of thematic focus 3 focuses on the evaluation of statistical processing of data obtained from non-invasive methodologies in the characterization of ancient geomaterials. Specifically, starting from case studies and different geomaterials, IR spectra have been acquired through various modalities and processed using multivariate statistics to assess whether it can be used for defining the origin of raw materials production techniques as well as for monitoring the degradation.

The activity of thematic focus 4 focuses on the development of shared diagnostic protocols for the study of archaeobotanical and palynological remains to reconstruct environments plant uses, adaptation strategies and processes of civilization and development of past societies.

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Thematic focus 1

- Developing protocols for characterization of plasters and mortars evaluation of the mechanical strength of mortars with optical microscopy
- Developing protocols for the study of deformations/alterations of historical surfaces
- Developing protocols for the study of complex architectural context using structural diagnostic techniques (GPR, TC, video-endoscopy, stereo photometry, laser scanner survey)

Thematic focus 2

- Developing protocols for micro-photogrammetric documentation of technological traces on-site
- Structuring micro-photogrammetry processes with at the mesoscale to achieve higher levels of detail and conduct qualitative analyses with 3D documentation
- Developing protocols for quantitative analysis of surfaces using micro-topographic investigation software

Thematic focus 3

- Developing protocols for the data processing phase has begun with data obtained from various IR modalities (transmittance in the laboratory, ATR, and Reflectance) to evaluate the use of IR reflectance analysis in situ for different materials in architectural and archaeological contexts

Thematic focus 4

- Developing protocols for the use of archaeobotany and palynology to enhance archaeological reconstruction, with particular focus on environmental dynamics, resource exploitation, commercial networks, and human resilience to environmental change.

1. Introduction

In the context of the direct study of architectural and archaeological heritage, in-depth diagnostic analysis is important both for the knowledge of the materials and the techniques of construction and processing than for knowledge of human activities of the past. Diagnostic study is the basis for the understanding of the mechanisms of interaction between the artifact and the conservation environment. It is essential for the interpretation of degradation phenomena, for the determination of conservation and maintenance choices, for the attribution of historical and cultural value of the findings.

In most cases, unfortunately, in-depth diagnostic interventions are performed at different times. They are entrusted to different operators and oriented to the evaluation of individual and specific problems. This makes the diagnostic data estate fragmented. Scientific data are almost always not properly linked to historical-archival knowledge.

The design definition of a diagnostics organically structured on the integration of different techniques and analytical measurements, selected, and combined according to the conservation needs of the artefact, is still lacking. The experimentation and sharing of diagnostic investigation protocols could facilitate a wider diffusion of a method oriented to the global knowledge of artefacts. The fragmentation of interventions would be avoided, and it would facilitate a reduction in the costs and time necessary to understand the conservation problems. To develop new diagnostic protocols in historical architectural contexts (thematic focus 1), ten representative case studies of Christian and medieval Roman churches have been selected: S. Prassede, S. Maria della Luce (the medieval S. Salvatore della Corte), S. Lorenzo in Lucina, S. Maria in Cosmedin, S. Giorgio in Velabro, S. Prisca, S. Giovanni a Porta Latina, S. Agnese f.l.m., Ss. Quattro Coronati, S. Paolo alle Tre Fontane. In the field of archaeology (thematic focus 2) the activities carried out within the project focused mainly on analysing stone, with some preliminary experiments also conducted on ceramic material. So far, the stone material has involved examining Roman and medieval inscriptions and early medieval sculpture. The first methodological protocols have been tested and applied at various archaeological sites, mainly associated with Sapienza University of Rome, in Italy: the medieval town of Cencelle; the cities of Falerii Veteres and Falerii Novi; the

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northeastern slopes of the Palatine Hill (Archaeological Park of the Colosseum); and the necropolis of Castel Sozzio

(VT). Abroad: The Basilica of the Holy Sepulchre in Jerusalem; two rock art sites in southern Ethiopia; the Ranaldi Shelter in Filiano (PZ); the rock sites in the Shaykh Kheder area in Kurdistan. Thematic focus 3 is focused on developing protocols in the IR analysis of geomaterials from the archaeological site of the Holy Sepulcher in Jerusalem; Pyrgi (Santa Marinella, Rome); Cencelle (Viterbo); Spoletino (Viterbo) and Battifratta (Poggio Nativo, Rieti) as well as experimental geomaterial samples. The thematic focus 4 It also contributes to the knowledge of contexts by developing protocols aimed at the analysis and environmental and social reconstruction of archaeological contexts through archaeobotanical and palynological investigations.

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2. Results

Significant results have been obtained in both architectural and archaeological contexts. In fact, diagnostic protocols have been defined for the study of stratified architectural contexts (Thematic focus 1), addressing different starting problems through the cross-use of different diagnostic techniques and previous historical documentary knowledge. For the case study of the basilica of S. Prassede in Rome, a protocol has been defined for the use of GPR technology on the ground and vertically for the verification of reconstruction hypotheses of the original configuration of the building. In the basilica of S. Lorenzo in Lucina it was possible to define a multi-method diagnostic protocol that involves the intersection of the results of different in situ diagnostic techniques (CT, GPR, video-endoscopy) with in-depth studies in the laboratory (characterization of materials in optical microscopy), aimed at understanding historical phases not yet investigated in the literature. In underground environments, a protocol for the diagnostic analysis of materials and the effects of humidity on their conservation has been developed. The set of investigations was closely related to the 3D model created from scratch using laser scanner technology, useful for understanding the connections between the hypogeal environments and the upper basilica and for locating all the points where the following punctual investigations were carried out: contact hygrometric measurements, characterization of materials by digital microscopy in situ, qualitative analysis of saline species. A similar protocol has also been defined for the case study of the basilica of S. Maria in Cosmedin, but with different purposes that pursue the evaluation of conservation aspects related to the presence of humidity. A work of analysis of the pavement in the same basilica as that conducted in S. Prassede, but with different results, was aimed at developing investigation protocols with GPR that help to reconstruct conservation history. In the case of the church of S. Maria della Luce, a diagnostic protocol that is based exclusively on non-invasive in-situ investigations (CT, GPR) has been defined to identify configurations prior to the last historical intervention of transformation of the building's rooms.

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The GPR investigations were aimed at defining experimental protocols for the study of vertical elements (pillars) and for the characterization of construction techniques. In San Giorgio in Velabro the use of GPR has been combined with that of ultrasound techniques, in order to verify the state of structural instability, producing an investigation procedure in which the two techniques are in some cases complementary. In the basilica of S. Prisca, again with GPR, investigation protocols have been developed aimed at tracing architectural elements incorporated into structures of subsequent construction. The use of the laser scanner for diagnostic purposes has been tested in the case studies of San Giovanni a Porta Latina and S. Agnese f.l.m. Other investigation protocols concerning the study of painted surfaces have seen spectrophotometry as a common technique, combined in some cases with observation in direct light and the use of the digital field microscope for a correct and complete characterization of the materials but above all the execution techniques.

In archaeological contexts (Thematic focus 2) the advancement in utilizing portable digital microscopes for micro-photogrammetry has played a crucial role in establishing new documentation protocols for fieldwork on mesoscopic and microscopic scales. A primary objective is to outline the particulars of this micro-photogrammetric approach and concentrate on evaluating its potential, advantages, and the level of detail attainable in the field of traceology, with a particular focus on on-site documentation.

Additionally, the field mission at the Ranaldi Shelter in Filiano (PZ) and the one carried out in southern Ethiopia on various rock art sites have enabled the implementation of a process to understand the degree of alteration of the paintings and to identify degradation through new documentation methods on a mesoscale.

At the same time, supervising the work of a master's student assigned a thesis on these topics is yielding new results in photogrammetric processing done in the lab with a stereomicroscope, aiming to achieve a 3D documentation of traces at higher magnifications and with ever better quality. At the same time, the study of ceramic surfaces was also expanded by testing micro-photogrammetry methods in museum settings and improving the quality and detail of the

documentation of incisions and excisions of about 0.5 mm, both on Linear B tablets from the Palace of Knossos and on Etruscan vases from the Villa Giulia Museum. The work on sculpture and architecture is still ongoing, but it is producing excellent results in terms of field documentation, knowledge of medieval craftsmanship and gestures, and methods of quantification using deep and machine learning.

Archaeological geomaterials have been characterized by IR spectroscopy. Mortars and stones from the archaeological site of the Holy Sepulcher in Jerusalem which are mainly composed of local carbonates; stone fragments from quarries and architectural sites in Jerusalem which are limestones and dolostones and hydraulic mortars from Israeli aqueducts from the sites of Caesarea, Tzipori, Susita, and Tiberias which are mainly composed of lime and crushed ceramics. Hydraulic mortars from Roman aqueducts in the city of Rome are mainly composed of lime and pozzolans. Volcanic and sedimentary rocks have been identified at the archaeological site of Pyrgi (Santa Marinella, Rome), whereas carbonates are mainly identified from the archaeological site of Cencelle (Viterbo). Ceramic samples from the archaeological site of Spolefino (Viterbo), Rio Tana (Lecce dei Marsi, Aquila) and Battifratta (Poggio Nativo, Rieti) have been analyzed and resulted to be composed of silicates and carbonates in different proportions. Finally, natural wakestone samples from the iconological site of Sezze (Latina) have been studied.

In addition, experimental samples: i) marble and travertine samples from quarries; ii) experimental mortar samples simulating Roman infrastructure; iii) mortar samples with organic additives extracted from microalgae and artificially aged ones; iv) mortar samples with acrylic additives and artificially aged ones have been analyzed at 0, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 17 and 21 months after exposure at natural environmental agents to check and monitor the degradation. IR spectra of experimental samples have been elaborated by PCA to test the diagnostic protocols.

In archaeobotanical field (thematic focus 4) the results currently focus on case studies:

Archaeological site of Leopoli-Cencelle

The archaeobotanical analyses on this site offer a fascinating look at the agricultural practices and use of natural resources by rural communities in northern Lazio between the 12th and 14th

centuries AD. Through the examination of plant remains, mainly charred, the diet, plant use and relationship with the surrounding environment have been reconstructed.

Archaeological excavations at the Holy Sepulcher in Jerusalem

Different levels of the archaeological site have been studied, yielding a good quantity of plant remains. A part of these was subjected to on-site palynological analysis to integrate the information already obtained from the examination of the macro-remains. The wood fragments recovered in the mortar have been also investigated following an integrated holistic approach.

The archaeological sites of Falerii Veteres and Falerii Novi

The study focused on *in-situ* palynological investigations for both sites. The ongoing excavation campaign carried out at *Falerii Veteres* has provided samples with macro remains that is now in study. The preliminary samples studied tell of an open environment with herbaceous plants, some of which are linked to the presence of man.

The northeastern slopes of the Palatine Hill (Archaeological Park of the Colosseum)

The palynological analyses have provided valuable insights into the local arboreal vegetation of ancient Rome, revealing the presence of several tree taxa typical of the Mediterranean landscape. Even more significantly, the pollen assemblages have highlighted a rich spectrum of herbaceous species thriving on the hill, many of which are indicative of anthropogenic disturbance and human activities. These data contribute to reconstructing both the natural setting and the dynamic interactions between vegetation and the long-term occupation of one of the most iconic areas of the city.

3. Methodology

The methodology followed for the development of innovative diagnostic protocols for the study of architectural contexts (Thematic focus 1) is based on the parallel identification of the need for in-depth knowledge of buildings in particularly complex contexts (such as the medieval religious architecture of Rome) and the most effective investigation techniques, mostly non-invasive in situ, used with a multi-method logic highly aimed at understanding specific historical and conservation issues representative of other similar cases. The various case studies were addressed from a diagnostic point of view by cross-referencing GPR and thermographic data, from video-endoscopy investigations and related to laboratory studies on the characterization of materials and evaluation of the conservative state by optical microscopy techniques. The fulcrum of the experimentation and the definition of the protocols has so far been that of the elaboration of the Diagnostic Project according to the specific needs of the investigation. The Diagnostic Project makes use of all the existing graphic and bibliographic documentation as a starting point, useful for the development of the protocol.

For the traceological study of stone and ceramic artifacts (Thematic focus 2), an experimental comparison collection was thus created. Moreover, to achieve this goal, we are conducting various tests in the field and in the laboratory, considering the different environmental and logistical conditions commonly encountered in the context of the archaeological documentation of technological traces. In particular, with the help of students from experimental archaeology master's courses, a series of experimentation processes have been developed to delve into ceramic materials. These processes led to the creation of a comparison collection for ceramics. This collection is based on the imprints left on ceramics by plants, fabrics, objects made of rope, wooden reeds, and even fingerprints. Everything was documented using various techniques, including macro and mesoscopic photogrammetry, as well as testing Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) to explore the usefulness of visual techniques for the initial assessment of surfaces. In addition, the documentation of bone materials uses the same methods, with adjusted light and angle settings to better capture the incisions on bone. The methods for quantifying surfaces

through metrological analysis are also being further developed.

These same techniques and digital documentation comparisons were then applied to stone materials and for on-site documentation.

For the study of geomaterials (Thematic focus 3) the activity focused on evaluating the statistical processing of data obtained from IR spectroscopies in the characterization of ancient geomaterials. The data processing phase has begun with data obtained from various IR modalities (transmittance in the laboratory, ATR, and Reflectance) to evaluate the use of IR reflectance analysis in situ for different materials in architectural and archaeological contexts. The processing of this extensive amount of data through a statistical approach (PCA) aims to demonstrate the technique's potential in analyzing geomaterials of interest in cultural heritage. Specifically, different data pre-processing methods are being evaluated to determine the most suitable one for minimizing the operator's influence.

For archaeobotanical studies (Thematic focus 4) dedicated approaches of archaeobotany and palynology were employed and carefully adapted to the specific characteristics of each context, with the aim of maximizing the likelihood of recovering material suitable for analysis.

The plant macro remains were extracted from the sediments through sieving or with the aid of a flotation machine depending on the characteristics of the site of origin and the type of remains. They are subsequently studied by stereomicroscopes and microscopes. The recognition of the plant occurs through morphological comparison of the diagnostic characters.

The treatment of the pollen samples is based on the partially modified procedure developed by Fægri and Iversen (1989). The morphological recognition of the pollen grains is carried out using transmitted microscopes at different magnifications.

4. Conclusions

The research carried out so far has led to the definition of new diagnostic protocols for the study of architectural and archaeological contexts. In the field of architecture, protocols have been defined, tested in four different case studies, but applicable in similar cases. An investigation protocol has been defined for the verification of the reconstructive hypotheses of architectural configurations prior to the current one starting from graphic restitutions of these configurations, using GPR technologies applied to the ground and vertically, experimented in the basilica of S. Prassede in Rome. A similar protocol, which also involves the use of thermographic technologies, and which is mainly based on direct observation of the structures, in the absence of graphic documentation of the historical phases, has been tested in the church of S. Maria della Luce in Rome. For the verification and understanding of historical phases traced but not yet thoroughly studied and documented, an investigation protocol has been developed that provides for the cross-referencing of diagnostic data from in-situ surveys with in-depth laboratory investigations, experimented in the basilica of S. Lorenzo in Lucina in Rome. A protocol for the study of conservation problems related to the presence of humidity has been defined and tested in the basilica of S. Maria in Cosmedin.

In the archaeological field, new approaches to tracer studies have been tested by means of digital micro-photogrammetry. An integrated approach of data from different types of plant remains was tested, offering a more complete and detailed view of the landscape, agricultural activities and the interaction between man and the environment in the archaeological site.

Transversal to architectural and archaeological contexts, the statistical processing of data obtained from IR spectroscopies in the characterization of ancient geomaterials is defining a diagnostic protocol that allows to establish the origin of raw materials and production techniques, useful data for planning conservation.

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